

Special Panel: Bridging City-Region with Multilevel Governance for Food System Transformation: A Research-Policy-Practice Dialogue

Today, there is a growing movement among diverse actors, from local governments and city networks to EU agencies and international organizations, advocating for a change in our food systems guided by agroecology principles. This movement spans multiple levels, from local initiatives to transnational efforts, highlighting a commitment to promoting urban food actions and recognizing the importance of the city-region level in a broader multi-actor landscape.

Despite these shared goals, there are notable contradictions and gaps in the current approach to food system transformation. On the one hand, there exists a potential for synergy among various actors working across different levels and regions, such as EU institutions, international food organizations, and city food networks. These groups are pointing to and addressing key food systems' problems, also showing commonalities in their efforts. On the other hand, the current landscape is characterized by fragmentation, lack of communication, and isolated approaches, making the future direction of food policy, governance, and advocacy in Europe uncertain.

The central question of our panel is how to address these contradictions and foster collaborative, synergistic relationships for concrete action in food system transformation. Specifically, we aim to explore:

- a) **Developing a Comprehensive European Food Policy:** We will discuss the current state and future of EU food system policy-making, including challenges, key objectives, and potential advancements under a new EU presidency and commission. This discussion will focus on integrating local-regional levels and agroecology and food system principles into a broader European framework.
- b) **The Role and Impact of Advocacy:** By reflecting upon the efforts of various organizations and campaigns, such as ARC2020 and the initiative for a "Towards a Common Food Policy for the EU" by IPES-Food, we aim to understand the limitations and successes in influencing policy and legislation, despite the presence of powerful opposing lobbies.
- c) **Envisioning Effective Food Governance:** The panel will consider current and more effective governance structures that could better facilitate diverse levels of engagement and representation in food system discussions. This involves identifying ways to include underrepresented groups, such as city-regions and marginalized actors, in governance processes.

This open panel invites all conference attendees and others interested in food system transformation for a meaningful exchange between researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders from various levels. Our discussion will be enriched by contributions from entities like Eurocities, FAO, IPES-food, the European Food Coalition and representatives from EU institutions involved in food policy and innovation.

INVITED SPEAKERS:

- **CALORI Andrea**, Està and Italian Network on urban food policies;
- **COSTE Madeleine**, EUROCITIES;
- **HEIDELBACH Olaf**, DG AGRI
- **MOYAERT Wim**, European Coordination Via Campesina
- **SCHAUVLIEGE Joke**, BE/EPP, NAT rapporteur on Sustainable food systems framework law

authors **TRIBOI Roxana** is a PhD architect and urban planner specialised on sustainable food planning, nature-based solution, urban agriculture, participatory planning and transdisciplinary action research and teaching. Currently, the food thematic evaluator of the European Urban Agenda for EU, she is also coordinating AESOP4food ERASMUS+, a transdisciplinary and participatory program on sustainable food planning for LE:NOTRE Institute, Netherlands.

RENTING Henk is connected as researcher-lecturer to AERES University of Applied Sciences in Almere, the Netherlands. He has a background in sociology and food studies and has been involved in various international projects on topics such as short food supply chains, city region food systems and inclusive food governance.

Dr MANGANELLI Alessandra works as a post-doctoral researcher in urban planning at the HafenCity University of Hamburg. Holding a PhD from the KU Leuven and VUB, she has been a consultant for the Committee of the Regions on the European Farm to Fork Strategy (Brussels, 2019-20) and she recently published a book by Springer on Urban Food Movements (<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-05828-8>). Representing AESOP SFP, she is partner member of the European Urban Agenda for EU Food Partnership.

keywords

- multi-level governance
- city-regions
- agroecology
- advocacy
- food policy
- Europe